

attacked more heavily than first-crop fields. Rice fields under shifting cultivation on hill slopes were not infested.

A study was made in 1973 kharif to determine the extent of infestation and the "hot spots" in Imphal, where most rice cultivation is confined.

The pest is well established in the major rice belt of Manipur, extending south to the Bishenpur block and north to Kangpokpi. Observations during the past 4 to 5 years confirm that the pest is building up in the state, necessitating regular chemical control as that for yellow stem borer and gall midge.

Further buildup of the pest cannot be ruled out, considering the changed agricultural strategy in Manipur brought about by the introduction of more high-yielding varieties, the extension of areas under such varieties, heavier fertilizer applications, and increased cropping intensity. Along with the rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis*, leaf butterfly is fast emerging as a pest at early growth stages of the second paddy crop — the bulk of rice production in the state. ■

Chemical control of the brown planthopper

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A study to determine suitable pesticides for control of the brown planthopper (BPH) was conducted in our field in kharif 1978.

The trial was laid out in a randomized block design, replicated four times. The insecticides fenitrothion, monocrotophos, ethion, and quinalphos at 0.05%

Brown planthopper incidence and rice yields on plots treated with various chemicals. Mangalore, India.

Treatment ^a	BPH (mean no./ 5 hills)	Mean yield (kg/plot)
Fenitrothion	27.2	2.0
Monocrotophos	15.2	2.3
Ethion	8.0	3.0
Quinalphos	35.2	1.8
Control	67.5	0.9
CD at 0.5%	12.57	0.22

^aAll treatments applied at 0.05%.

concentration were compared with an untreated control. They were sprayed at crop growth stages from the nursery to the hard dough stage. The BPH on five randomly selected hills per replication were counted before and periodically after each spraying.

All the insecticidal sprays significantly reduced BPH infestation and increased yields over that of the control (see table). Treatments with ethion were most effective, followed by those with monocrotophos and fenitrothion. ■

Hopperburn by the orange-headed leafhopper in Bangladesh

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In Bangladesh, hopperburn caused by the brown planthopper, whitebacked planthopper, and green leafhopper was previously reported. This is the first report on hopperburn caused by the orange-headed leafhopper (OHLH) *Thaia oryzivora* Ghauri.

Ghauri (1962) described the new genus *Thaia* and the new species *Thaia oryzivora* on paddy in Thailand. Smaller than *Nephotettix* spp., OHLH can be easily identified by its orange-colored head and subhyaline fore wings. This leafhopper was first recorded in Bangladesh — on wheat in 1964 and on rice in 1968 — by H. Z. Alam. Ahmed and Samad (1972) regarded the insect as a pest of economic importance in Bangladesh. It usually feeds on the undersurface of leaves, causing necrotic lesions around feeding sites. The badly affected leaves show white scars or irregular lines on the upper surfaces. Adults and nymphs produce similar damage. Alam and Alam (1977) reported that the insect breeds actively in October and November and again in February and March, producing high populations during those periods.

Hopperburn occurred the last week of March in areas with controlled irrigation in the Dacca area. There was standing water in the fields and rice growth was luxuriant. Hopperburn occurred from flowering to the hard dough stage in IR8, especially that planted in November or

early December. It did not occur on BR3, BR6, and Pajam II. Although OHLH caused negligible hopperburn, it is a potential pest of rice in Bangladesh. ■

Chironomid fauna of Korea and their role in the rice agroecosystem

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Chironomids are the most numerous insects in the rice paddy ecosystem in Korea. However, the significance of chironomid fauna in the ecosystem is not known.

In the summer 1975, Yasumatsu and Chang collected chironomids in the rice paddies of Suweon, Korea. Hashimoto identified the specimens as follows:

1. *Smittia* sp.
2. *Mesosmittia* (?) sp.
3. *Chironomus nipponensis* Tokunaga
4. *Chironomus plumosus* Linnaeus
5. *Syncricotopus rufiventris* (Meigen)
6. *Cricotopus trifasciatus* Panzer
7. *Harnischia* sp.
8. *Orthocladus suspensus* Tokunaga
9. *Eukiefeeriella* sp.

The only chironomid species previously reported from Korea is *Chironomus oryzae* Matzumura. But it was not identified by a specialist. We believe that the species identified as *Chironomus oryzae* is *C. plumosus*. More material is still under taxonomic study by Hashimoto, and more species will later be added to the list.

Most species of chironomids breed in dead organic matter and the adults emerge in large numbers. Predators, such as spiders and damselflies, feed on them and also on pests that breed on the rice plant (see figure).

Chironomids are significant to the agrosystem. Throughout the vast rice areas of Asia they serve as an alternative food of predators and thus help conserve predators when rice pests are scarce. Chironomids are often more abundant and easily captured than rice pests.